
THE ASSESSMENT OF THE FACTORS THAT IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCES PRACTICE ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG THE ACADEMICS STAFFS IN UNIVERSITY COLLEGE INSANIAH.

ADEJARE YUSUFF AREMU.

PhD. Scholar, Othman. Yeop Abdullah Graduate School of Business, University Utara Malaysia

Dr. ARFAN SHAHZAD

Senior Lecturer, Yeop Abdullah Graduate School of Business, University Utara Malaysia

ABSTRACT

The summary review of this research work it is as follows here, the main purpose of this study is to analysis the assessment of the factors that impact of human resources practice on job satisfaction among the academics staffs of University College Insaniah. There are some factors that examined in this study work, which are : Mainly some factors influenced job satisfaction opportunity, human resources planning, recruitment and selections, compensations and performance appraisal. The staffs were obtained from the human resource department of the University for this purpose, it consist just view department, which are: Muamalat, Multimedia, Hospitality and others, the staffs consist of 45 Malaysian, 1 Indonesian and 1 Bangladesh, and others 3 academics staffs. There were males and females staffs employed by Insaniah.

Primary data was used in this study, Primary data referred to information that is first obtained by the researcher on the variables of interest for specific purpose of the study. For the purpose of this study, primary data were obtained through the distribution of questionnaire to all the academics staffs of Insaniah.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Human Resources Planning, Recruitment and Selections, Compensations and Performance Appraisal, Insaniah University.

INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

Human resource (or personnel) management is the sense of getting things done through people. It's an essential part of every manager's responsibilities, where many organizations find it advantageous to establish a special division to provide an expert service dedicated to ensuring that the human resource function is performed efficiently

The impact of human resource management (HRM) practices popularly known as HR practices on organizational performance and employee attitudes has been a leading area of research in the developed world for years (Delaney and Huselid, 1996; Huselid, 1995; Katou and Budhwar, 2007; Petrescu and Simmons, 2008)). But surprisingly, very limited number of studies have been conducted on HR practices in the context of developing countries in general (Schuler as cited in

Budhwar and Debrah, 2001, Sing, 2004, Yeganeh and Su, 2008) and Malaysia in particular (Mahmood, 2004). This study aims to fill the existing research gap and to explore the relationship between HR practices and job satisfaction in the context of Insaniah University.

Academicians, researchers, policy-makers, practitioners, students (local and foreign) likewise Entrepreneurs of Malaysia and other developing countries could benefit from this study by exploring the relationship between HR practices and job satisfaction. This study intends to augment the contemporary research and practice of human resource management. Furthermore, it would also be useful for the developed countries as they find developing countries (like Malaysia) as attractive places for investment due to their large markets, and cheap and skilled workforces (Budhwar and Debrah 2001). While Job satisfaction often refers to a collection of attitudes about specific factors of the job. Employees can be satisfied with some elements of the job while simultaneously dissatisfied with others. Moreover, job satisfaction is a life satisfaction. The most referred definition of job satisfaction was offered by Locke (1976) who defined job satisfaction as a pleasing or positive emotional state resulting from the evaluation of a person's work (Haque and Taher, 2008). Work fulfillment is additionally characterized as a singular's general state of mind with respect to his or her employment (Robbins, 1999). Mullins (1993) specified that inspiration is firmly identified with employment fulfillment. Different components, for example, a worker's needs and yearnings, social connections, style and nature of administration, employment plan, pay, working conditions, saw long range opportunities, and saw opportunities somewhere else are thought to be the determinants of occupation fulfillment (Byars and Rue, 1997; Moorhead and Griffin, 1999). Work fulfillment has a critical impact on representatives' hierarchical duty, turnover, non-attendance, lateness, mischances, and grievances (Byars and Rue, 1997; Moorhead and Griffin, 1999). As indicated by Robbins (1999), a fulfilled workforce can increment authoritative efficiency through less diversion brought about by non-attendance or turnover, couple of rates of ruinous conduct, and low therapeutic expenses.

One of the greatest preludes to the investigation of employment fulfillment was the Hawthorne studies. These studies (1924–1933), fundamentally credited to Elton Mayo of the Harvard Business School, looked to discover the impacts of different conditions (most eminently light) on scholastics staff' profitability. These studies at last demonstrated that novel changes in work conditions briefly build efficiency (called the Hawthorne Effect). It was later found that this increment came about, not from the new conditions, but rather from the learning of being watched.

The finding of study gave solid confirmation that individuals work for purposes other than pay, which prepared for analysts to research different elements in occupation fulfillment. Exploratory administration (otherwise known as Taylorism) additionally had a huge effect on the investigation of employment fulfillment. Frederick Winslow Taylor (1911), Principles of Scientific Management, contended that there was a solitary most ideal approach to perform any given work errand. This book added to a change in mechanical creation methods of insight, bringing on a movement from talented work and piecework towards the more current of sequential construction systems and time-based compensations. The beginning utilization of investigative administration by commercial enterprises significantly expanded profitability on the grounds that scholastics staffs were compelled to work at a quicker pace. Be that as it may, scholastics staff got to be depleted and disappointed, in this way leaving scientists with new inquiries to answer in regards to employment fulfillment. It ought to likewise be noticed that the work of W.L. Bryan, Walter Dill Scott, and Hugo Munsterberg set the tone for Taylor's work.

1 Background of the Study

HR showcasing learning ought to incorporate enrollment and worker fulfillment strategies utilizing viable correspondence systems. Learning will likewise incorporate procedures, for example, needs appraisals and fulfillment assessments. General business and human asset assignment information is an unquestionable requirement aptitudes and capacities.

- Skills incorporate the capacity to effectively tune in, utilization rationale to distinguish qualities, shortcomings and opportunities. Furthermore, marking abilities and solid composed, verbal and presentation correspondence skill are needed.

HR showcasing capacities contain oral and composed perception and expression. The capacity to talk and compose plainly, so as to adequately impart, is crucial.

Capabilities.

- A degree in HR or advertising can give competitors strategies, apparatuses and methods needed to acquire organization objectives and goals. The HR showcasing position obliges a hopeful why should capable utilization consultative methodologies and procedures keeping in mind the end goal to hold representatives and draw in new ability.

- Qualified HR promoting competitors will have aptitudes in composing, math, business, HR, advertising, relationship building and marking.

(HR) is concerned with the issues of overseeing individuals in the association.

The Human Resources division is in charge of numerous individuals' related issues in an association.

Under the HR division's transmit are the accompanying parts:

- The procedure of enlisting suitable possibility for the association, Identifying and meeting the preparation needs of existing staff, guaranteeing representative welfare and worker relations are sure, guarantee the workplace is alright for workers.

The Human Resources Department likewise covers five key parts.

- Executive part – in this part the HR office are seen as the experts in the regions that incorporate Human Resources or individuals administration.

- Audit part – in this limit the HR office will check different divisions and the association in general to guarantee all HR strategies, for example, Health & Safety, Training, and Staff Appraisal and so on are being done as per the organization's HR arrangement.

- Facilitator part – in this part, the HR division help or encourage different offices to accomplish the objectives or norms as laid out in the HR arrangements of the association. This will include preparing being conveyed for issues that emerge in the ranges identifying with individuals administration.

- Consultancy part – the HR office will prompt administrators on the most proficient method to handle particular overseeing individuals issues professionally.

- Service part – in this limit the HR division is a data supplier to bring issues to light and educate offices and useful zones on changes in policy.

2 Problem Statements

The study on job satisfaction helps to know their preference and problem of the employees. Mainly some factors influenced job satisfaction opportunity, human resources planning, recruitment and selections, compensations and performance appraisal. When these factors are

high, job satisfaction will equally be rated as high in any organization. When these factors are low, job satisfaction is said to be low as well. So the needs of the employees are carefully studied by conducting survey on job satisfaction towards the organization. This study is very useful and helpful to know the problem faced by the employees and also know the employee requirements in an organization.

Work fulfillment is the mix of emotions and conviction that scholastics staff hold in connection to their present employments. A specialist with abnormal state of fulfillment will for the most part like their employment; they feel that they are by and large genuinely treated and trust that the occupation has numerous attractive features (Jones et al. 1999). The fulfillment at work has been described as a positive or satisfying passionate state which rises as the aftereffect of assessing one's work or encounters in the working environment. It is accepted that human asset practices are firmly connected with occupation fulfillment (Ting, 1997). Researchers and experts trust that sound human asset practices result in better level of occupation fulfillment which at last enhances authoritative execution (Appelbaum, Bailey, Berg and Kalleberg, 2000). Work fulfillments are likewise connected with different elements, for example, truancy (Hackett and Guion, 1985; Hulin, 1991), turnover (Carsten and Spector, 1987), satisfaction (Boehm and Lyubomirsky, 2008) and association duty.

Regardless of different study on employment fulfillment, the commonness and indicators on the effect of human asset hones towards work fulfillments among scholastics staff still should be exhaustively inspected. Along these lines, the center of this study is to inspect the employment fulfillment among the scholastics staff of Insaniah University.

3 Scope of Study

The survey of study is to be generalized by using the primary data in distributing questionnaire to the staffs in order to facilitate the intended result for this study and its successful accomplishment.

4 Significance of the Study

The study may be beneficial both for the organization and the employees. Various departments can benefit by knowing the employees level of satisfaction. For the employees indirectly helps them to convey their expectations regard this project highlights the scope for future improvement in above requirements provided to the employees.

The present study is noteworthy in two ways that is hypothetical and pragmatic. The hypothetical perspective demonstrates a few trades hypothesis by looking at the impact of HRM practices work fulfillments on Insaniah staffs. As per this hypothesis, there is a relationship in the middle of workers and the association and this respond shapes the reacts of the representatives. On the off chance that the discoveries of the present study are right, this hypothesis is accepted. For this situation when the association has the capacity give great HRM practices and ready to improve work fulfillment of its kin, they will respond by not captivating in practices that are not positive to the associations. In these words, they will take part in positives correspondence. For occurrences, where representatives trust they are dealt with decently in working spot, then they, hold positives states of mind towards the association (moorman, 1991). The pragmatic perspective will demonstrate that the discoveries are right, they will have the capacity to help HR supervisors to outlined measures that will demoralize staffs from taking part in working spot

abnormality practices. For cases, this study needs to demonstrate how HRM practices can be enhanced to help diminish event or awful living up to expectations place environment.

5 Research Questions

Consistent with the discussion so far, this study seeks to answer the following questions on academics staff job satisfaction at Insaniah University.

- (i) Does human resource practice affect the academics staff job satisfaction in Insaniah?
- (ii) Which human resource practice has the most impact in determining academics staff job satisfaction?

6 Research Objectives

The main objective of the study is to examine the impact of human resource practices to job satisfaction on the academic staffs of Insaniah University. Hence, the objectives of this study are listed below:

- (A). To determine the effect of human resource planning on academics staff jobs satisfaction in Insaniah.
- (B). To determine the effect of recruitment and selection on academics staff job satisfaction in Insaniah.
- (C). To determine the effect of training and development on academics staff job satisfaction Insaniah.
- (D).To determine the effect of performance appraisal on academics staff job satisfaction in Insaniah.
- (E). To determine the effect of compensation on academics staff job satisfaction in Insaniah.
- (F). To determine the effect of employee relations management on academics staff job satisfaction in Insaniah.
- (G). To determine the effect of safety and health management on academics staff job satisfaction in Insaniah.
- (H). To determine the effect of employee benefits on academics staff job satisfaction in Insaniah.

7 Organization of the Study

This study is structured into five chapters. The first chapter consists of Introduction, problem statement, research questions and research objectives, scope and significance of the study.

Chapter two covers the literature reviews, past studies review and theoretical perspectives related to the research area.

Part three exhibits the exploration system for the study. The part talks about the exploration configuration and strategy of the study. The part goes further to talk about the choice of the respondents, test size, advancement of poll for the exploration and information gathering method. The part closes with a brief depiction of the techniques and methodology that were utilized to investigate information accumulation from the overview.

Part four talks about the translation of the exploration discoveries. The outcomes are abridged in various tables to encourage translation.

Part five, the last section talks about the translation of the examination discoveries from the study. The discoveries from this study are contrasted with those found in Past examination looked into in part two. Section five closes with administration Implications and a few recommendations for future exploration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2 Introduction

This chapter discusses the concept of job satisfaction, human resource management, human resource practices, human resource planning, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, compensation, employee relation, safety and health issues relating job satisfaction. The literature review is conducted in a systematic manner to unfold the disciplines of human resource management and job satisfaction.

2.1 The Concept of Job Satisfaction

Work fulfillment is the most generally talked about issue in the field of hierarchical conduct. A few researchers characterized occupation fulfillment as a general mentality of the specialists constituted by their methodology towards the wages, working conditions, control, advancement relate with the employment, social relations in the work, acknowledgment of ability and some comparative variables, individual trademark, and gathering relations separated from the work life (Blum and Naylor, 1986). Be that as it may, Locke (1976) characterized employment fulfillment as joy or positive passionate state coming about because of the evaluation of one's occupation or occupation experience. While Robbins (1999) apparent employment fulfillment as a singular's general demeanor with respect to his or her occupation. In a more extensive perspective, Hoppock (1935), demonstrate that occupation fulfillment implies the mental, physical and natural fulfillment of worker and the degree of employment fulfillment can be known by inquisitive representatives about the employment fulfillment degrees.

The scholastic meanings of occupation fulfillment can be partitioned into three sorts as beneath:-

- (i) Integral definition: This definition underlines specialists' occupation disposition towards environment with central consideration on the mental change for individual occupation fulfillment of worker (Lock, 1976; Fogarty, 1994; Robbins, 1996).
- (ii) Differential definition: It underlines work fulfillment and the distinction between the genuine merited prizes and the normal prize from representatives; the bigger contrast implies the lower fulfillment (Smith et al., 1969).
- (iii) Reference structure hypothesis: It underscores the way that the target attributes of associations or occupations are the essential variables to impact worker's working state of mind and practices yet the subjective sensibility and clarification of working representatives about these goal qualities; the said sensibility and clarification are likewise influenced without anyone else's input reference structures of individual worker (Morse, 1953; Homans, 1961). With the clarification above, it is straightforward that occupation fulfillment is the aggregate of the assessments related with the employment that is performed. In the event that a man trusts that their qualities are acknowledged inside of the employment, they have an inspirational demeanor towards the occupation and obtain work fulfillment. Different speculations of employment fulfillment have been produced by analysts and administration researchers.

2.2 Human Resource Management

Human asset administration (HRM), which is characterized as 'beneficial utilization of individuals in accomplishing the association's vital business destinations and the fulfillment of individual worker needs' (Stone 1998), alludes to the strategies and practices included in

completing the human asset part of an administration position including arranging, employment examination, enrollment, choice, introduction, remuneration, execution evaluation, preparing and advancement and work relations (Dessler, 2007). It is made with approaches, practices and frameworks that impact representatives' conduct, state of mind, and execution (Noe, et. al., 2008). HRM specialists contend that a company's choice on HRM is dictated by a scope of outer and interior elements, for example, political, lawful, financial and social variables, methodology, structure, industry, size, monetary proprietorship and experience (Pauwe and Dewe 1995).

2.3 The Theories of Job Satisfaction

Having examined in point by point on the different meanings of fulfillment, it is just as critical to investigate the distinctive demeanors and reactions laborers will reflect towards their occupations. This really decides the level of employment fulfillment of an individual has towards his or her occupation. For this specific reason, researchers and scientists have delivered thorough speculations in light of employment fulfillment. The point was to give a system to seeing the variables impacting such demeanors, as well as why it brings about such impacts:

Frederick Herzberg's two variables Theory Hertzberg et al. (1959) fundamental two-variable hypothesis of inspiration proposed that fulfillment and disappointment were not the two inverse extremes of the same continuum, yet two different substances created by very distinctive aspects of work – these were named as "cleanliness components" and "sparks". Cleanliness variables are described as outward segment of occupation outline that add to representative disappointment on the off chance that they are not met. Illustration incorporates supervision, working condition, organization arrangements, compensation and relations with associates. Helpers, be that as it may, are natural for the occupation itself and incorporate angle, for example, accomplishment, improvement, obligation and acknowledgment. These characteristic variables have long been recognized as vital determinants of inspiration.

2.4 Human Resource Practices and Jobs Satisfaction

There has been broad open deliberation in the writing over the impacts of HRM on employment fulfillment. In a few studies, work fulfillment has been distinguished as a key variable interceding any positive relationship between human asset hones and authoritative execution (Guest, 2002). It accepted that human asset practices are firmly connected with employment fulfillment (Ting, 1997), on the grounds that numerous researchers and experts trust that sound human asset practices result in better level of occupation fulfillment which at last enhances hierarchical execution (Appelbaum, Bailey, Berg and Kalleberg, 2000).

2.5 Human Resource Planning and Job Satisfaction

Human asset arranging is characterized as the technique by which an association guarantees that it has the right number and sorts of HR at the perfect spot and at the ideal time (Decenzo and Robbins, 1999). Studies have been done by investigates to look at the relationship between human asset arranging and employment fulfillment. Case in point, Ahmad and Khalil (2007) thought about the human asset arranging of two banks of Bangladesh - Dutch Bangla Bank Ltd. furthermore, Agrani Bank. They watched that neither of the banks had any composed human asset arranging. Aswathappa (2008) contended that an association ought to have better human asset arrangements to rouse its workers.

2.6 Recruitment and Selection and Job Satisfaction

Enlistment and choice is a piece of a procuring procedure which decides the choices as to which competitors will get livelihood offers. Enlistment is a procedure of creating a pool of qualified contender for a specific occupation, while determination is the procedure of making a "contract" or "no contract" choice with respect to every candidate for a vocation. The procedure regularly includes deciding the qualities needed for viable employment execution and after those measuring candidates on those attributes.

2.7 Training and Development and Job Satisfaction

Preparing is characterized as the arranged intercession that is intended to improve the determinants of individual execution. Preparing is identified with the aptitudes regarded fundamental by the administrations of an association, which must be procured by the individuals from that association, to enhance the profitability and accomplishing its objectives. Preparing offered to representatives, may help them diminish their tension or dissatisfaction, brought on by work requests that they are not acquainted with, and they are deficient with regards to the abilities to handle it viably (Chen et al., 2004).

2.8 Performance Appraisal and Job Satisfaction

Execution examination speaks to a focal capacity of human asset administration and has remained a critical point of examination among Organizational specialists (Dulebohn and Ferris, 1999). Since the convenience of execution examination as an administrative choice instrument depends somewhat on regardless of whether the execution evaluation framework has the capacity gives exact information on representative execution, rating precision is a basic part of the evaluation process. Execution examination includes the recognizable proof, estimation and administration of human execution in associations. For the most part, associations conduct evaluations for regulatory as well as formative purposes. As far as regulatory reason, the evaluations are utilized as the premise for a choice about the representative's work condition, including advancements, end, and prizes.

2.9 Compensation and Job Satisfaction

Pay is a key human asset administration capacity (Rynes et al., 2002) where it might be characterized from authoritative, individual, and dialect points of view. As far as dialect, pay is known as compensation and pay, compensation, prize and/or pay framework is frequently utilized reciprocally as a part of associations (Henderson, 2006; Milkovich and Newman, 2008). Taking into account a singular's point of view, remuneration is seen as non participation and enrollment compensates that are essentially required by workers to meet their fundamental needs and enhance ways of life in the public eye (Henderson, 2006; Maurer et al, 1995).

2.10 Employee Relation and Job Satisfaction

A decent worker connection includes giving a reasonable and steady treatment to all representatives with the goal that they will be focused on the association. Organizations with great worker relations are prone to have human asset technique that places a high esteem on representatives as partners in the business. Workers who are dealt with as partners have notable rights inside of the association and can expect treated with poise and appreciation. Successful

worker relations obliged collaboration in the middle of administrators and worker connection delegates to mutually agree to the representative connection approach, which is a strategy intended to convey administration's reasoning and works on concerning worker related matters and keep issues in the working environment from turning out to be more genuine.

2.11 Safety and Health and Job Satisfaction

The motivation behind wellbeing and wellbeing administration is to distinguish dangers chances and minimize those dangers to the representatives, environment and the general population. The guideline here is to help recognizing best practices and executing nonstop change. Basically, expanding safe practices and diminishing at-danger practices through distinctive parts of generation framework is an objective of security and wellbeing administration. Regarding security and wellbeing administration, chiefs frequently endeavor to guarantee wellbeing and wellbeing preparing and examine all occurrences to focus their underlying drivers so that powerful remedial activities are executed. In extra, it additionally oversees change, identifying so as to include new assembling procedures, items and acquisitions and minimizing the dangers coming about because of the change, with the reason for settling on fitting choices for development, measuring precisely wellbeing and security execution has a noteworthy part (Azadeh et al., 2008).

2.12 Employee Benefit and Job Satisfaction

Incidental advantages can effect work fulfillment in a few ways. In the first place, incidental advantages stand as a vital part of specialist remuneration. In like manner to the National Compensation Survey led in USA by the Bureau of Labor Statistics, it was assessed that advantages made up 30 for each penny of aggregate pay for all the nation regular citizen specialists in 2006 (Adams, 2004). A few advantages, for example, Social Security and Medicare, the nation's openly gave elderly annuity and wellbeing protection, are lawfully obliged and make up about 27 for every penny of all advantage pay. The remaining 73 for each penny of advantage remuneration is contained basically of paid leave, protection arrangements and retirement and reserve funds arranges. These advantages are regularly not subject to tariff and are, subsequently, less expensive to increase through a business than through the business (Alpert, 1987).

2.13 Summary

Part two of this study explored the applicable writing of human asset practices and fabricates a top to bottom comprehension for the hypothetical ramifications on occupation fulfillment. The above audit additionally demonstrates that there have been a few studies directed comprehensively concentrating on human asset practices and occupation fulfillment. A general finding is that, for basically all the human asset hones, the principle impacts on employment fulfillment are sure and factually huge. Be that as it may, studies depicting the effect of human asset rehearses on occupation fulfillment have yet gotten legitimate consideration in Malaysia. This study has been embraced to fill the current exploration hole.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3 Introduction

This chapter discusses the method used to examine relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The part further layouts the hypothetical structure, populace and test, exploration outline, speculation advancement, wellspring of information, information accumulation, estimation and instrumentation and information investigation. At long last, the outline of the methodology is examined.

3.1 Population

As the unit investigation of the study is at individual level, the populace embodies scholastics staffs utilized by Insaniah. These staffs were utilized into the different divisions of the University. The staffs' positions range from departmental level and the framework from the HR at Insaniah. There were no inspecting methods set up for the study as it is a contextual analysis research with moderately little populace. All staffs were for this study. The staffs were obtained from the human resource department of the University for this purpose. The staffs consist of 45 Malaysian, 1 Indonesian and 1 Bangladesh, and others 3 academics staffs. There were males and females staffs employed by Insaniah.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

The hypothetical system for this study is set up after precisely considered the examination inquiries, targets and survey of pertinent writing in the past part. Henceforth, the system concentrates on the human asset rehearses that could have affected at work fulfillment among scholastics staffs at Insaniah University.

The research framework of the study is depicted as follow:

To achieve the research objectives, a survey approach using questionnaire is used to elicit information from respondents who are the academics staffs of insaniah University.

3.5 Sources of Data

Primary data was used in this study. Primary data referred to information that is first obtained by the researcher on the variables of interest for specific purpose of the study. For the purpose of this study, primary data were obtained through the distribution of questionnaire to all the academics staffs of Insaniah.

3.9 Summary

This part depicted the improvement of the examination routines for this study. The examination philosophy and the exploration outline have been clarified with theory improvement, poll advancement and information gathering system. Further to that, the information examination procedures were likewise clarified.

RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the results of the study using descriptive and inference statistics. It begins with descriptive statistics, followed by factor analysis, reliability test, t-tests and regression analysis.

		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Valid	Muamalat	21	42.0	42.0	42.0
	Multimedia	14	28.0	28.0	70.0
	Hospitality	5	10.0	10.0	80.0
	Others	10	20.0	20.0	96.0
Total		50	100.0	100.0	100.0

4.1.3 Nationality Of Respondent

		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Valid	malay	45	90.0	90.0	90.0
	indonesia	1	2.0	2.0	92.0
	bangladesh	1	2.0	2.0	94.0
	others	3	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.3 highlights descriptive statistics of the main variables of the study. As seen, the respondents generally perceived that they are most satisfied with performance appraisal (mean = 3.1533, SD = 1.08841) and compensation (mean = 3.0867, SD = 1.17959). This is followed by perceived undecided or moderately satisfied with human resource planning (mean = 3.1100, SD = 1.05361), training and development (mean = 3.0600, SD = 1.05361), recruitment and selection (mean = 3.4200, SD = 1.02311) and safety and health (mean = 3.1800, SD = 1.15903). However, respondents perceived that they are neutral in terms of employee benefit (mean = 3.5733, SD = 0.93808) and employee relation (mean = 3.2200, SD = 1.16955). Overall, respondents perceived that they are moderately satisfied with their job (mean = 3.5306, SD = 1.24335).

Table 4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

	<i>N</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
HumanResource	50	1.00	4.50	3.1100	1.05361
recruitment	50	1.33	5.00	3.4200	1.02311
Tranig	50	1.00	4.67	3.0600	1.19084
employeerel	50	1.00	4.67	3.2200	1.16955
compensation	50	1.00	4.67	3.0867	1.17959
performance	50	1.00	4.33	3.1533	1.08841
jobsatisfaction	49	1.00	5.00	3.5306	1.24335
employeebenefit	50	1.33	5.00	3.5733	.93808
safetyhealth	50	1.00	4.67	3.1800	1.15903
Valid N (listwise)	49				

4.2.2 Reliability Statistics

<i>I.V</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
H.R. PLANNING	0.928	4
RECRUTMENT AND SELECTION	0.895	3
TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT	0.867	3
PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL	0.938	3

4.2.2 Reliability Statistics

<u>I.V</u>	<u>Cronbach's Alpha</u>	<u>N of Items</u>
COMPENSATION	0.941	3
EMPLOYEE RELATION	0.916	3
SAFETY AND HEALTH	0.950	3
EMPLOYEE BENEFIT	0.787	3
D.V		
EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION	0.818	1

4.3 T-Test

T-Tests were performed to think about employment fulfillment between gatherings, to be specific nationality, position and division level of scholastics staffs in KUIN. As highlighted in the above tables, the outcomes showed that T-Test result is noteworthy for nationality gathering taking into account $p > 0.016$, for Malaysia (8.16) , Indonesia and Bangladesh (2.79) and others (1.50) staffs. This demonstrated that Malaysia had higher employment fulfillment contrasted with Indonesia and Bangladesh and others staffs.

Table 4.4.4 Model Summary

<u>Model</u>	<u>R</u>	<u>R Square</u>	<u>Adjusted R Square</u>	<u>Std. Error of the Estimate</u>	<u>Durbin-Watson</u>
1	.873 ^a	.763	.715	.66375	2.042

Table 4.4.5 ANOVA^b

<u>Model</u>		<u>Sum of Squares</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>Mean Square</u>	<u>F</u>	<u>Sig.</u>
1	Regression	56.582	8	7.073	16.054	.000 ^a
	Residual	17.623	40	.441		
	Total	74.204	48			

Generally speaking, the outcomes for relapse investigation are noteworthy, at $p < .000$. The human asset rehearses (EB, COM, ER, RS, SH, HRP, PA, and TD) in the proposed model uncovered around 2 percent of the watched difference in staff work fulfillment. At the end of the

day, around 98 percent of the varieties of staffs' occupation fulfillment are not delineated in the model. The regression analysis revealed only compensation is marginally significantly related with staffs job satisfaction (.064, based on $p=0.05$) as indicated in Table 4.4.5 above.

Testing of Hypothesis

The formulated hypotheses are hereby tested below:

Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results	
Hypothesis	Testing
H1: Human resource planning affects staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	REJECTED
H2: Recruitment and selection affects staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	REJECTED
H3: Training and development affects staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	REJECTED
H4: Performance appraisal affects staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	REJECTED
H5: Compensation affects staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	REJECTED
H6: Employee relation affects staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	REJECTED
H7: Safety and health affects staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	REJECTED
H8: Employee benefits affect staffs job satisfaction at KUIN	ACCEPTED

4.6 Summary

This section examined the consequences of the study. Discoveries from the study indicated that remuneration is a determinant of KUIN scholastics staffs work fulfillment. Further examinations on the discoveries will be exhibited in Chapter Five.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

The consequences of examination relating to each of the exploration theories were displayed in past part. This section talks about conclusion and suggestions in light of the discoveries of the study. Constraints and suggestions for future examination are likewise talked about.

5.1 Discussions of Findings

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that impact on human resource practices of academics staffs on job satisfaction. The eight human resource practices being examined are human resource planning, recruitment and selection, training and development, performance appraisal, compensation, employee relation, safety and health, and employee benefit on job satisfaction. The findings and results are discussed on one hand, and compared with previous literatures on the other.

The discoveries of this study authenticate the discoveries of past examination on the effect of remuneration on employment fulfillment. Case in point, studies done by Ago, Mueller and Price (1993), Sire and Balkin (2000), Weiner (1980), Adams (1963, 1965), Bloom (1999), Mani (2002) demonstrated that there exists an in number relationship in the middle of remuneration and employment fulfillment. Results from different studies have kept on supporting that remuneration is one of the most grounded determinants of representative dispositions, inspiration and practices (Gerhart and Milkovich, 1992). Proper assignment of pay structure was additionally said to have a critical effect on employment fulfillment (e.g., Adams, 1963, 1965; Bloom, 1999; May et al., 2002).

Dismissal of every single different hypothes (aside from H5) in this study reasoned that all other human asset practices did not fundamentally impact staffs work fulfillment in KUIN. The dismissal proposed that the discoveries of this study couldn't bolster the discoveries exhibited in Chapter 2, for example, Greenhaus et al., 1991, Hodgart, 1994, Fernandez, 1992, Hunter and Schmidt, 1982, Neumann et al., 1989, Jones et al. 2009, Fried and Ferris, 1987, Cropanzano and Folger, 1996, Shiang et al., 2009, Trevino and Weaver, 2001, Azadeh et al., 2008, Kilic and Selvi, 2009, Pohlen and La Londe, 1994, Carraher and Carraher, 2005; Carraher et al., 2008; Konopaske and Werner, 2005; Roolaht, 2006; Scarpello and Carraher, 2008; Sturman and Carraher, 2007, which found that human asset arranging, enrollment and determination, preparing and advancement, execution evaluation, worker connection, wellbeing and wellbeing and representative advantages were fundamentally identified with employment fulfillment. The unimportant of these human asset hones in the connection of laborers employment fulfillment are some way or another defended as by and large the movement of outside specialists was predominantly with the end goal of acquiring however much cash as could reasonably be expected to give a superior living to their family in their nation of root.

5.2 Limitation of the Study

The real impediment in this study identifies with the specimen size of the study. As the study intends to investigate the element that effect on human asset hones on scholastics staffs in KUIN, the extension is essentially restricted to remote and neighborhood workers in the University. Because of the little specimen, the outcome demonstrates that the neighborhood staffs are ruled in the University and if consideration is not taken the worldwide staff must be exceptionally cautious with their employment in KUIN. Dialect boundary is another confinement for this study. The instrument is outlined in English dialect. Along these lines, dominant part of the respondents are thinking that its hard to react as a result of the dialect obstruction. Regardless of these confinements, this study has the capacity serve as an establishment for future studies in different associations or Universities on a bigger scale. It is positively worth to investigate further, particularly inside of association that utilized a generous number of outside specialists.

5.3 Recommendations for Future Study

In view of writing audit on human asset practices and employment fulfillment, a proposed examination model was created for this study. A sum of eight components in human asset administration were utilized as autonomous variables, while work fulfillment of staffs was utilized as indigent variable. Aside from the suggestions for future study clarified in the administrative ramifications area, the analyst might likewise want to propose a longitudinal exploration outline for future study to focus the impact of human asset hones on both scholastics

and non-scholastics staff or specialists' employment fulfilment. Longitudinal information got after some time would likely deliver plausible causation as opposed to affiliation.

In extra, future exploration in view of subjective study is likewise suggested. Ideally it will expand the comprehension of the effect of human asset rehearses on occupation fulfillment among scholastics staff in Malaysia.

It is additionally prescribed that an extended study to incorporate bigger example of nearby and outside laborers in KUIN specifically, or Universities when all is said in done so as to sum up the discoveries and suggestions to the staff's populace on the loose. The examination model of this study can be re-tried in different business associations which utilized staffs.

5.4 Conclusion

The reason for this study has been satisfied with both the examination inquiries addressed and research goals accomplished, in spite of the proposed model possibly clarified the varieties rate of the autonomous variables on the indigent variable to be specific, staffs work fulfilment in KUIN. Future study has been proposed to investigate different indicators that may add to the employment fulfilment of the staffs in the associations.

Further to that, the analysis and results of the study shown that compensation is the only human resource practices that affect staffs job satisfaction in KUIN. Therefore, KUIN should channel more effort and resources in managing its compensation policy and compensation structure. This could bring great impact on the level of job satisfaction among staffs, which may ultimately enhance the staffs commitment, reducing absenteeism, staff turnover, increase productivity and improve organizational performance.

REFERENCES

2. Acton, T. and Golden, W. (2003), "Training the knowledge worker: a descriptive study of training practices in Irish software companies", *Journal of European Industrial Training*, Vol. 27, Nos 2-4, pp. 137-46.
- Adams, J.S. 1963. *Toward an understanding of inequity*. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology* 67, no. 5: 422–36.
3. Adams, J.S. 1965. "Inequity in Social Exchange." In *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, ed. L. Berkowitz, 267–299. New York: Academic Press.
4. Adams, S. (2004), "Employer-provided health insurance and job change", *Contemporary Economic Policy*, Vol. 22 No. 3, pp. 357-69.
5. Agho, A. C, Mueller, C. W., & Price, J. L. (1993). *Determinants of employee job satisfaction an empirical-test of a causal model*. *Human Relations*, 46(S), 1007-1027.
6. Ahmad, I., Khalil, M. I., *Human resource planning in the banking sector of Bangladesh: A comparative study between public & private bank*. *Journal of Business Administration*, Vol.33, No.3&4, pp.23-42, 2007.
7. Akerlof G., Rose A. and Yellen J. (1988) 'Job Switching and Job Satisfaction in the US Labor Market', *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity* 2: 495– 582.

8. Angle, H. & Perry, J. (1981). *An empirical assessment of organisational Commitment and organizational effectiveness*. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 26 (1), 1-14.
9. Appelbaum, E. (2002). *'The impact of new forms of work organization on workers'*, in G. Murray, J. Belanger, A. Giles and P. Lapointe (eds), *Work and Employment Relations in the High-Performance Workplace*, London: Routledge.
10. Arthur, W., Bennet, W., Edens, P.S. and Bell, S.T. (2003), "Effectiveness of training in organizations: a meta-analysis of design and evaluation features", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 88, pp. 234-45.
11. Aswathappa, K., *Human resource management: Text and cases*. Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited, 2008.
12. Austin, W. and Walster, E. (1974), "Participants' reactions to equity with the world", *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, Vol. 10, pp. 528-48.
13. Aydemir, A. and Skuterud, M. (2008), "The immigrant wage differential within and across establishments", *Industrial & Labor Relations Review*, Vol. 61 No. 3, pp. 641-72.
14. B.E. Becker, B. Gerhart, "The Impact of Human Resource Management on Organizational Performance: Progress and Prospects", *Academy of Management Journal*, 39, 4, 779-801 (1996).
15. B.E. Becker, M.A. Huselid, *High Performance Work Systems and Firm Performance: A Synthesis of Research and Managerial Implications*, In G. R. Ferris (Ed). *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, Greenwich: Jai Press, 16, 53-101 (1998).
16. Babakus, E., Yavas, U., Karatepe, O. and Avci, T. (2003), "The effect of management commitment to service quality on employees' affective and performance outcomes", *Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 31 No. 3, pp. 272- 87.
17. Balakrishnan, T. and Hou, F. (1999), "Socioeconomic integration and spatial residential patterns of immigrant groups in Canada", *Population Research and Policy Review*, Vol. 18, pp. 201-17.
18. Bateman, T.S., and Strasser, S. (1984), 'A Longitudinal Analysis of the Antecedents of Organizational Commitment,' *Academy of Management Journal*, 27, 95–112.
19. Bates, S. (2004). *Getting Engaged: Half of Your Workforce May be Just Going Through the Motions*. *HR Magazine*, 44-51. Bedeian, A.G. and Armenakis, A.A. (1981), "A path-analytic study of the consequences of role conflict and ambiguity", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 417-24.

20. Behrman, D.N. and Perreault, W.D. (1982), "Measuring the performance of Industrial salespersons", *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 10 No. 3, pp. 355-70.
21. Bhuian, S. N., & Abdul-Muhmin, A. G. (1997). *Job satisfaction and organizational commitment among "guest-worker" salesforces: The case of Saudi Arabia*. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 10(3), 27–44.
22. Bies, R.J., and Shapiro. D.L. (1987). *Interactional fairness judgements: The influence of causal accounts*. *Social Justice Research*, 1(2):199-218.
23. Bloom, M. and Michel, J.G. (2002), "The relationships among organizational context, pay dispersion and managerial turnover", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 45 No. 1, pp. 33-42.
24. Blum, M. and Naylor, J. (1986), *Industrial Psychology: Its Theoretical and Social Foundation*, Harper and Row, New York, NY. Boehm.
25. J. K., & Lyubomirsky, S. (2008). *Does happiness promote career success?* *Journal of Career Assessment*, 76(1), 101-116
26. Boselie, P. and Van der Wiele, T. (2002), "Employee perceptions of HRM and TQM, and the effects on satisfaction and intention to leave", *Managing Service Quality*, Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 165-72.
27. Boxall, P. and Macky, K. (2007), "The relationship between 'high-performance work practices' and employee attitudes: an investigation of additive and interaction effects", *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 18 No. 4, pp. 537-67.
28. Bratton, J. and Gold, J. (1999), *Human Resource Management*, 2nd ed., Macmillan Business, London.
29. Brockner, J. (1988), 'The effect of work layoffs on survivors: Research, theory and practice'. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 10, pp. 213-255.
30. Brockner, J., Davy, J. and Carter, C. (1985), "Layoffs, self-esteem, and survivor guilt: motivational, affective, and attitudinal consequences", *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, Vol. 36, pp. 229-44.
31. Brooke Jr., P. P., Russell, D. W. and Price, J. (1988), 'Discriminant validation of measures of job satisfaction, job involvement, and organizational commitment'. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 73,0. 2, pp. 139-145.
32. Brown, S. P. (1996). *A meta-analysis and review of organizational research on job involvement*. *Psychological Bulletin*, 120, 235–255.

33. Burke, R. and Green glass, E. (1999), '*Work-family conflict, spouse support, and nursing staff well-being during organisational restructuring*'. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, No. 4, pp. 327-336.
34. CCH Asia (2009). *Managing Performance : Featuring Poor Performance*. Kuala Lumpur, CCH Asia Pte Limited. C. Ostroff, *The Relationship Between Satisfaction, Attitudes, And Performance: An Organizational Level Analysis*. *Journal Of Applied Psychology*, 77, 963-974 (1992).
35. Caldwell, D.F. and O'Reilly, C.A. (1990), "*Measuring person-job fit with a profile-comparison process*", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 75, pp. 648-57.
36. Campbell, D.J., Campbell, K.M. and Chia, H.B. (1998), "*Merit pay, performance appraisal, and individual motivation – an analysis and alternative*", *Human Resource Management*, Vol. 37 No. 2, pp. 31-146.
37. Carraher, S.M. and Carraher, S.C. (2005), "*Felt fair pay of small to medium, sized enterprise (SME) owners in Finland and Latvia: an examination of Jaques' equity construct*", *Journal of Small Business Strategy*, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 1-8.
38. Carraher, S.M., Sullivan, S.E. and Crocitto, M. (2008), "*Mentoring across global boundaries: an empirical examination of home- and host-country mentors on expatriate career outcomes*", *Journal of International Business Studies*, Vol.8, pp. 1310-26.
39. Carsten, J.M. and Spector, P.E. (1987), "*Unemployment, job satisfaction, and employee turnover: a meta-analytic test of the Muchinsky model*", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 72, pp. 374-81.
40. Cartwright, S. and Holmes, N. (2006). '*The meaning of work: the challenge of regaining employee engagement and reducing cynicism*'. *Human Resource Management Review*, 16: 2, 199–208.
41. Chew, K.H. and Basu, S. (2005), "*The effects of culture and HRM practices on firm performance. Empirical evidence from Singapore*", *International Journal of Manpower*, Vol. 26 No. 6, pp. 560-81.
42. Chew, Y. (2005), "*Achieving organizational prosperity through employee motivation and retention: a comparative study of strategic HRM practices in Malaysian institutions*", *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management*, Vol. 13 No. 2, pp. 87-104. 99
43. Chu, C, Hsu, H. M., Price, J. L. and Lee, J. Y. (2003), '*Job satisfaction of hospital nurses: an empirical test of a causal model in Taiwan*', *International Nursing Review*, Wol. 50, pp. 176- 182.

44. Churchill, G.A., Ford, N.M. and Walker, O.C. (1974), “*Measuring the job satisfaction of industrial salesmen*”, *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 11, August, pp. 254-60.
45. Clark, A.E. (2001), “*What really matters in a job? Hedonic measurement using quit data*”, *Labour Economics*, Vol. 8 No. 2, pp. 223-42.
46. Clegg C. W. (1983) ‘*Psychology of Employee Lateness, Absence and Turnover: A Methodological Critique and an Empirical Study*’, *Journal of Applied Psychology* 68: 88–101. Cobb, A.T. and Frey, F.M. (1996), “*The effects of leader fairness and pay outcomes on superior/subordinate relations*”, *Journal of Applied Social psychology*, Vol. 26, pp. 1401-26.
47. Cohen-Charash, Y. and Spector, P.E. (2001), “*The role of justice in organizations: a meta-analysis*”, *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, Vol. 86 No. 2, pp. 278-321. Colford, J. (2005, Sept. 12). *The ROI of safety*. *Business Week*
48. Collins, A.B. (2007), “*Human resources: a hidden advantage?*”, *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 19 No. 1, pp. 78-84.
49. Cranny, C. J., Smith, P. C, and Stone, E. F. (1992). *Job satisfaction: How people feel about their jobs and how it affects their performance*. New York, NY: Lexington Books.